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Review Article

A Review Of The Dragon Fruit's Nutritional Composition, Health Benefits And It's Pharmaco-therapeutic Benefits

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ABSTRACT

Dragon fruit is considered a tropical fruit with an extraordinary appearance, and it has gained widespread popularity due to its health claims. This review investigates the nutritional information of dragon fruit as there is evidence indicating that the fruit is rich in vitamins, minerals, and fiber. Furthermore, it consists of a wide range of antioxidant compounds such as betalains and phenolic which help combat inflammation. The antioxidant effects exhibited by dragon fruit have high implications for the lives of human beings. These compounds are capable of scavenging harmful free radicals, thereby reducing oxidative stress and damage to the cell. This might help in the avoidance of chronic diseases like cardiovascular disease, cancer, and neurodegenerative diseases. Also, the high amount of fiber in dragon fruit can enhance bowel health, help with blood sugar levels, and assist with controlling weight. Another area that holds promise in dragon fruit is its prebiotic capabilities. The fruit has resistant starch and colonic insoluble carbohydrates which can be used as the energy source for the beneficial bacteria in the gut. This can contribute to the enhanced microbiota diversity in the gut, enhanced nutrient absorption, and boosted immunity. Also, investigators have considered the possible treatment utilization of dragon fruit. It has been suggested that it may have hypoglycemic, hypolipidemic, and hepatoprotective effects. Moreover, the anti-inflammatory effect of dragon fruit can be useful for the control of inflammatory diseases.

INTRODUCTION

Plants of the Cactaceae family are easily distinguished from other plant kingdom groups due to their unique look and delicate feel. Because their edible fruits have been a part of the human

diet for more than 9,000 years, the vine (climbing) cactus (*Hylocereus* species) is among the most significant members of this family ^[1]. Due to its health and therapeutic properties, dragon fruit, pitaya, strawberry pear (*Hylocereus* spp. and

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Selenicereus spp.), or kamalam, is becoming a super crop globally, even in marginal terrain. It is simply a climbing cactus vine, originating in Central and South America, resistant to pests and diseases, and tolerant to abiotic stressors. It has several benefits, such as low water and nutrient requirements, comparatively low resources needed for orchard establishment and upkeep, the ability to produce fruit multiple times a year, the potential to maintain a high yield for up to 20 years, a high benefit-to-cost ratio, and high nutritional and functional qualities (such as being high in antioxidants and fibers) [2]. The dragon fruit types and variations that are now accessible in our nation are primarily imports from other nations. In India, gardeners mostly cultivate red-skinned fruits with white pulp (93%) (*Hylocereus undatus*), although extremely small-scale production is done for fruits with red peel and red meat (6.5%) (*Hylocereus monacanthus*) and yellow peel and white flesh (≤ 0.5) (*Hylocereus megalanthus*) [3].

Origin And Distribution Of Dragon Fruit

By spreading through birds and peoples for fruit production, *H. undatus* became widely distributed throughout the Americas and the Caribbean prior to the arrival of the Spanish. Native to tropical and sub-tropical forest regions of Mexico, Central America, and Northern South America, the pitaya, sometimes known as dragon fruit, is widely spread and naturally exists there. The Spanish brought this fruit to the Philippines in the sixteenth century, and a French priest brought it to Indochina in the middle of the nineteenth century (it had previously been in Vietnam, Laos, and Cambodia). Later, it adapted and became a major fruit crop in the area because of the favorable climate. It later rose to prominence as a fruit crop in Southeast Asia and is currently grown extensively in tropical and subtropical regions. From its birthplace, it has expanded to several nations. Numerous nations, including Australia, Cambodia, China, Colombia, Ecuador, Guatemala, Hawaii, Indonesia, Israel,

Malaysia, New Zealand, Peru, the Philippines, Taiwan, Thailand, Spain, Sri Lanka, and Vietnam, have successfully adopted dragon fruit production. This fruit crop was very recently introduced in India, and a small number of producers have begun to cultivate it in regions such as Maharashtra, Karnataka, Gujarat, West Bengal, etc. Vietnam is now the world's largest producer and exporter of dragon fruit. Pitaya fruits are now imported into India from Thailand and Vietnam [4]. Recently brought to India, the fruit of the dragon is a super fruit that is thought to be a fruit crop with great potential and rewards. The fruit is very colorful, has a fluffy flesh, and a black, edible seed with a wealth of nutrients packed in it. It draws growers of the fruit crop, which comes from Mexico and Central and South America, from various regions of India. In India, hardly much study has been done on this fruit crop. Dragon fruit has a great deal of potential for export to other nations. In India, very few farmers have started growing dragon fruit in the states of Tamil Nadu, Maharashtra, Gujarat, Andhra Pradesh, and Karnataka [5].

Nutritional Composition Of Dragon Fruit

According to the ICAR-National Institute of Abiotic Stress Management, the typical nutritional value of ripened dragon fruit is given in Table 1.

Table 1: nutritional composition of dragon fruit [6].

Si.no	Nutrient	Amount (per 100 g)	Daily value (%)
1.	Water	87 g	-
2.	Protein	1.1 g	2.1
3.	Fat	0.4 g	-
4.	Carbohydrate	11.0 g	3.4
5.	Fiber	3 g	12
6.	Vitamin B1 (thiamine)	0.04 mg	2.7
7.	Vitamin B2 (riboflavin)	0.05 mg	2.9
8.	Vitamin B3 (niacin)	0.16 mg	0.8
9.	Vitamin C (ascorbic acid)	20.5 mg	34.2
10.	Calcium (Ca)	8.5 mg	0.9
11.	Iron (Fe)	1.9 mg	10.6

12.	Phosphorus (P)	22.5 mg	2.3
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Health Benefits

Dragon fruit has relatively low levels of saturated, trans, and cholesterol fats. Consequently, purchasing this fruit revitalizes and sustains heart health over time. Additionally, it lowers body weight. In addition, its seeds have polyunsaturated fats and omega 3 and omega 6 fatty acids, all of which are good for a healthy lifestyle. Additionally, it is rich in antioxidants, which lower cholesterol and have other advantages. Thus, it offers a decent option to avoid the negative effects of LDL cholesterol. It is commonly known that proteins serve as the building blocks of bodily cells, ensuring the body's proper operation. Dragon fruit has a lot of protein. First of all, proteins are broken down and digested by enzymes to become simple proteins, which improve metabolism, strength, and weight loss while also hastening cell repair and supporting muscle in the body^[7]. It has a deep cultural history and has been used for millennia as a traditional medicine to treat a variety of degenerative disorders, such as inflammation, brain dysfunction, arthritis, and arteriosclerosis. Additionally, dragon fruit has shown encouraging antimicrobial and antibacterial qualities. The remarkable antioxidant activity of dragon fruit makes it stand out and is essential for reducing the risk of chronic diseases. Numerous phytochemicals, which serve as antioxidants and combat harmful free radicals, are found in the fruit. The body is protected from the consequences of oxidative stress by this protective mechanism. Interestingly, the dragon fruit's bark has an even greater quantity of bioactive substances with strong antioxidant qualities. From a pharmacological and nutritional perspective, this unique characteristic is highly intriguing since it may provide a natural supply of antioxidants for a range of medicinal uses^[8].

Pharmaco-Therapeutic Benefits Of Dragon Fruit

Anti-Oxidant Properties

The oil that is derived from *H. undatus* seeds and peels is a vital source of antioxidant chemicals, and the peels contain more flavonoids than the pulp. Because of their higher antioxidant activity, *Hylocereus polyrhizus* species have a high phenolic content of around 15.92 mg gallic acid/g. After examining the antioxidant properties of dragon fruit, it was concluded that participants with pre-diabetes and normocholesterolemia who ate red pitaya had lower overall antioxidant status^[9]. Two species of *Hylocereus*, *Hylocereus polyrhizus* (red dragon fruit) and *Hylocereus undatus* (white dragon fruit), were examined for their antioxidant qualities in their fruits (peels and pulps). Compared to fruits (peels and pulps) of the two *Hylocereus* species, pulps had greater levels of ascorbic acid and total phenolic. Pulp of *H. undatus* $\approx$ pulp of *H. polyrhizus* > fruit (peel and pulp) of *H. polyrhizus* > fruit (peel and pulp) of *H. undatus* is the order of the anti-radical power as determined by 2,2-diphenyl-1-picryl hydrazyl (DPPH) radical scavenging activity. The following is a ranking of the ferrous ion chelating activity: *H. undatus* pulp > *H. polyrhizus* fruit (pulp and peel) > *H. undatus* fruit (pulp and peel) > *H. polyrhizus* pulp. Ascorbic acids and phenolics both enhanced the anti-radical properties of the two *Hylocereus* fruit species, although the latter made a greater contribution. The pulp of *H. undatus* exhibited the best antioxidant qualities when considering ferrous ion chelating and free radical scavenging activities^[10].

Red-flesh dragon fruit has strong antioxidant qualities, which are even stronger than those of white-flesh species. Additionally, both dragon fruit species' peels have exceptional antioxidant capacity. It is hypothesized that betacyanin, the pigment found in dragon fruit, may be responsible for the antioxidant qualities. In addition to its

ability to change color, betacyanin offers additional health advantages. In addition to phenolic acids, flavonoids, and betacyanin, dragon fruit is abundant in tocopherol and ascorbic acid (vitamin C), two more potential natural antioxidants. With its antioxidant properties attributed to organic peroxy radicals. This response has to do with its primary biochemical role. Tocopherol can shield tissue lipids from damage caused by free radicals. These free radicals can be produced from polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFAs) in lipoproteins or membrane phospholipids following the elimination of hydrogen during the oxidation start phase [11]. Despite being nearly ten times more prevalent in peels than in meat, betacyanins had the strongest antioxidant activity in both the DPPH and FRAP tests. Therefore, structural diversities and/or compositional variations between the edible and non-edible sections of fraction 1's components were emphasized. Lastly, in contrast to the results measured for the entire extracts, polyphenolic fractions of meat and peels were shown to be able to inhibit all of the food-borne pathogens examined, including yeasts and molds [12].

Hypoxia is the primary cause of the rise in lactic acid levels following intense physical activity. The drop in oxygen levels in muscles is known as hypoxia. Anaerobic metabolism provides energy under hypoxic conditions. Lactic acid levels rose in rats that received treatment for excessive physical exercise. Acute muscle deoxygenation and ischemic-reperfusion are indicated by the purine catabolism into xanthine that occurs as the amount of lactic acid rises. Free radicals are created and accumulate as a result of xanthine oxidation being triggered by purine catabolism and ischemia-reperfusion. Strong physical activity produced free radicals, which were suppressed by a sufficient supply of antioxidants. Lactic acid levels were indirectly lowered by the antioxidant in RDF extract. In rats given intense exercise, red

dragon fruit extract lowers lactic acid levels and CK activity. Two possible dosages for lowering lactic acid and CK activity were 300 and 200 mg/kg [13].

Anti-Microbial Properties

Water-soluble betacyanins with a purplish-red hue are abundant in red pitahaya fruit. Using HPLC, the impact of 4°C refrigeration on the betacyanin content of red pitahaya was tracked daily for a week. After six days of storage at 4°C, the red pitahaya's betacyanin level rose by 57.2%. While the betanin concentration rose from $37.9 \pm 1.6\%$ to $42.7 \pm 1.5\%$ between days 2 and 7, the phylloactin content dropped from $45.4 \pm 1.5\%$ to $38.3 \pm 3.1\%$. The broth microdilution test was used to measure the antimicrobial activity, which was then represented as the minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC). Fruits refrigerated for 6 days at 4°C showed superior antibacterial activity (MIC values: $3130\text{--}6250 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) against 10 pathogenic Gram-positive and 6 Gram-negative bacteria than the newly harvested fruits (MIC values: $50,000\text{--}>50,000 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$). At concentrations of $0.39\text{--}3.13 \text{ mg mL}^{-1}$, betacyanin-rich extract was also tested against normal human cell lines (HEK-293 and THP-1) and was not cytotoxic. In conclusion, six days of refrigeration raised the amount of betacyanin, altered its composition in red pitahaya, and enhanced its antibacterial action [14].

An extract from dragon fruit leaves exhibits antibacterial efficacy against *Streptococcus pneumoniae*, *Neisseria meningitidis*, and other meningitis germs *monocytogenes* (*Listeria*). When it came to meningitis bacteria (*Neisseria meningitidis*, *Streptococcus pneumoniae*, and *Listeria monocytogenes*), red dragon fruit leaf extract showed more potential antibacterial activity than white dragon fruit leaf extract [15].

Mice with burn injuries were used to test the in vivo antibacterial activity of red dragon fruit peel extracts. Along with wound-healing properties, the

extract demonstrated a synergistic inhibitory effect with chloramphenicol on *P. aeruginosa* growth. Globally, there is increasing worry over the frequency of dengue infection. Using molecular docking, it has demonstrated a good correlation between betanin, a phytoconstituent found in dragon fruit, and the inhibition of dengue virus NS2B/NS3 protease. Viral replication is therefore inhibited by the inhibition of viral protease). Dragon fruit may therefore be one of the all-natural treatments for infectious disorders [16]. Bacteria of various kinds reacted to the various extracts in varied ways. The current investigation showed that every bacterium examined was susceptible to distinct extracts from pitaya fruit peels with red and white meat. The chloroform extracts of the peels of both *Hylocereus* species had the strongest antibacterial activity, with the peel of *H. polyrhizus* exhibiting higher antibacterial activity than that of *H. undatus*. Regarding the two extracts, red flesh pitaya peel chloroform extract (RCE) is an excellent source of strong natural antibacterial agents that work against both Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria [17].

Anti-Inflammatory Properties

The potent antioxidant activity of betalains found in red dragon fruit peels may be the cause of their potent anti-inflammatory properties. Free radicals and other reactive oxygen species are important pro-inflammatory mediators because they initiate or maintain inflammatory processes (inflammatory cascade); as a result, scavenging free radicals reduces the inflammatory response [18]. The chorioallantoic membrane (CAM) vascular irritation assay was used to assess the activity of betalains that were encapsulated in maltodextrins. It was shown that betalains encapsulated in maltodextrin-pectin or maltodextrin-gum Arabic matrices reduced vascular irritation five to six times more effectively than betalains that were not

encapsulated. Vascular irritation was caused by sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS). Since free radicals are the main pro-inflammatory mediators and the inflammatory process is maintained in their presence (inflammatory cascade), the potent anti-inflammatory activity of betalains from *H. polyrhizus* peels can be attributed to the potent antioxidant activity. Additionally, scavenging free radicals can reduce the inflammatory response [19].

Anti-Diabetic Properties

In a cause-effect study, the anti-insulin-resistant properties of red pitaya were examined in insulin-resistant rats treated with fresh pitaya and two heat-processed pitaya samples with varying amounts of phenolic contents, scavenging activities, and soluble dietary fibers over a 6-week treatment period. The findings demonstrated that the insulin resistance, hypertriglyceridemia, and atherosclerotic alterations brought on by a fructose supplement in rats were considerably ($p < 0.05$) reduced by fresh pitaya. Pitaya with a poor antioxidant content that was thermally processed for 30 minutes at 95°C substantially ($p < 0.05$) reduced hyperinsulinemia [20].

The results showed that eating red pitaya fruit has a lot of promise and helps type 2 diabetic people regulate their blood glucose levels and lipid profiles, with varying effects on each variable. Compared to the 600 g quantity (28.89%), the 400 g amount was more successful in reducing triglyceride levels, with a larger percentage of changes (37.14%). However, the 600 g quantity was more successful in raising the HDL cholesterol level (14.95%) and lowering the blood glucose (34.87%), total cholesterol (31.64%), and LDL cholesterol (41.04%) [21]. The findings demonstrated that in excess nutritional conditions, the red dragon fruit (*Hylocereus polyrhizus*) was successful in lowering fasting blood sugar levels. The red dragon fruit (*Hylocereus polyrhizus*) can also help people with excess nutritional status

(obesity and overweight) decrease their systolic and diastolic blood pressure [22].

Anti-Cancer Properties

Antioxidant activity and the concentration of various components in methanol and water extracts were examined. Additionally, an anti-inflammatory assay based on NO generation in the RAW 264.7 macrophage model was conducted, along with cytotoxic action against cancer and normal cells of skin, prostate, and gastrointestinal origin. Additionally, the interaction of the primary drug carrier in blood human serum (HSA) was used to assess the quenching capabilities of fruit polyphenols. The correlations between the obtained parameters were shown through the use of chemometric analysis. Compared to dragon fruits from Thailand, those picked in Israel had stronger antioxidant qualities and a higher overall concentration of betacyanins and polyphenols. The fruits from both origins that were analyzed had strong cytotoxic action against prostate and colon cancer cells but no anti-inflammatory or toxic impact on healthy cells. Moreover, aqueous extracts of dragon fruits showed a strong binding capacity to HSA. All of these predestined dragon fruits are potential additions to a regular diet that are both aesthetically pleasing and chemopreventive [23]. The cytotoxic and antioxidant properties of pitaya (*H. polyrhizus* and *H. undatus*) peel supercritical carbon dioxide extracts were examined, and their composition was evaluated by GC-MS. β -amyrin (15.87%), α -amyrin (13.90%), octacosane (12.2%), and γ -sitosterol (9.35%) were the main components of *H. polyrhizus* extract, whereas β -amyrin (23.39%), γ -sitosterol (19.32%), and octadecane (9.25%) were the main contents of *H. undatus*. It was discovered that the primary constituents of the two extracts, β -amyrin, β -sitosterol, and stigmast-4-en-3-one, were in charge of the wide spectrum of cytotoxic activities they displayed against PC3, Bcap-37, and MGC-803 cells. With IC₅₀ values of 0.83 and

0.91 mg/mL, respectively, they also exhibited modest DPPH radical scavenging activity [24].

The production of gold nanoparticles by biosynthesis using dragon fruit extract (DF extract) is a sustainable method of producing gold nanoparticles. The purpose of this study was to examine the fruit's anticancer properties and its capacity to produce gold nanoparticles. Transmission electron microscopy, Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy, X-ray diffraction, and UV-vis spectrophotometry were used to analyze the produced gold nanoparticles. The biogenesis of DF extract-capped gold nanoparticles (DF-AuNPs) in the 10–20 nm size range is supported by the XRD and TEM data. While there was no discernible cytotoxic impact on MDA-MB-231 cells, the DF extract and DF-AuNPs significantly inhibited the development of MCF-7 breast cancer cells [25]. To examine the phytoconstituents and anticancer potential of *H. undatus* fruit extracts, followed by apoptotic tests on HepG-2 cells. Anti-proliferation properties and qualitative phytochemical profiling of aqueous chloroform. Dragon fruit pulp extracts in ethyl acetate, hexane, and methanol were tested. Methanol extract was further used for apoptotic research by treating HepG-2 cells for nuclear labeling using DAPI and GC-MS analysis to clarify the existence of active chemicals in response to the findings of anti-proliferation investigations. Carbohydrates, tannins, saponins, anthocyanins, quinones, cardiac glycosides, terpenoids, triterpenoids, phenols, acids, and other compounds were found by qualitative phytochemical examination and steroids in fruit extract in water. Carbohydrates, saponins, alkaloids, cardiac glycosides, triterpenoids, phenols, and coumarins were also detected in chloroform fruit extract. Carbohydrates, tannins, saponins, flavonoids, alkaloids, anthocyanins, cardiac glycosides, terpenoids, triterpenoids, acids, and steroids were also present in ethyl

acetate fruit extract. Hexane fruit extract included acids, quinones, phenols, anthocyanins, carbohydrates, and saponins. However, methanol fruit extract included other phytochemicals, including phenols, glucose, tannins, saponins, flavonoids, alkaloids, anthocyanins, cardiac glycosides, terpenoids, triterpenoids, acids, and steroids. The aqueous extract's IC₅₀ value was 112.43 µg/ml, the chloroform extract was 99.13 µg/ml, the ethyl acetate extract's was 102.68 µg/ml, the hexane extract's was 83.96 µg/ml, and the methanol extract's was 69.09 µg/ml in a 24-hour incubation period. Using DAPI staining, the methanol fruit extract of *H. undatus* revealed bright pieces of a nucleus, which are indicative of apoptosis. According to GCMS data, the methanol extract contains 43 aromatic chemicals, some of which may be polyphenolic compounds [26].

One of the most common malignancies worldwide and the primary cause of cancer-related deaths among women is breast cancer. Utilizing the bioactive ingredients in functional meals helps lower the chance of developing chronic illnesses like cancer and heart disease. The present investigation assessed the antioxidant capacity and the impact of pitaya extract (PE) on the expression of BRCA1, BRCA2, PRAB, and Er α in breast cancer cell lines (MCF-7 and MDA-MB-435), as well as on cell survival, colony formation, cell cycle, and apoptosis. PE had high anthocyanin (74.65 $\pm$ 2.18) and antioxidant activity levels. In the MCF-7 (ER+) cell line, we saw a specific reduction in cell growth brought on by PE. According to cell cycle studies, PE caused the G₀/G₁ phase to grow and the G₂/M phase to shrink. PE also inhibited the expression of the BRCA1, BRCA2, PRAB, and Er α genes and caused apoptosis in the MCF-7 (ER+) cell line. Lastly, we show that following PE treatment, MDA-MB-435 cells (ER-) showed no change. When considered collectively, the current research

indicates that pitaya could offer some protection against breast cancer [27].

Anti-Obese Properties

In this experiment, twenty-seven female Wistar rats were employed. Nine rats served as the control group, while groups two and three consisted of eighteen obese rats each. Standard feed CP 551 was given to group 1 (control group), a high-fat diet to group 2, and a high-fat diet plus 100 mg of red dragon fruit flesh extract per kilogram of body weight to group 3. Rats' body weight change and physical characteristics were the parameters that were measured and documented weekly. Following 30 days of feeding, blood samples were taken for lipid profile analysis, fecal fat and cholesterol analysis, and visceral fat and organ weight measurements. According to the results, rats in Group 3 had significantly lower body weight, Index Obesity Lee, organ weight, visceral fat weight, total cholesterol, low-density lipoprotein (LDL), triglycerides, VLDL, and the ratio of total cholesterol/HDL than rats in Groups 1 and 2. At the same time, rats in Group 3 had significantly higher concentrations of HDL cholesterol, fat, and fecal cholesterol than rats in Group 1 and Group 2. The flesh extract from red dragon fruit was found to have hypolipidemic and anti-obesity properties, as well as the potential to reduce inflammation and oxidative stress [28].

This article aimed to find out how red dragon fruit peel powder changed the weight, total cholesterol, triglycerides, high-density lipoprotein (HDL), and low-density lipoprotein (LDL) of male hyperlipidemic Balb-C mice. A fully randomized design (CRD) was employed in this investigation, with four replicates for every dosage treatment. Red dragon fruit peel powder was administered to 24 male mice in six groups, including positive and negative controls, at dosages of 50, 100, 150, and 200 mg/kg BW every day. For 20 days before receiving therapy, mice were fed a high-fat diet until they developed hyperlipidemia. For 30 days,

the powdered red dragon fruit peel was administered orally along with gavage. Samples of blood were extracted from the vena caudalis tail. BioLABO kits were used for enzymatic analysis of blood lipid samples. The findings of this investigation show that following the administration of red dragon fruit peel powder for 30 days, triglycerides, LDL-c, and total cholesterol levels all dropped. Additionally, it was demonstrated that dragon fruit powder can raise HDL-c levels. According to the study's findings, male Balb/c mice with hyperlipidemia can have their blood lipid levels improved by using powdered red dragon fruit peel [29].

Anti-Viral Properties

There is currently no viable medication for the global epidemic known as COVID-19. This illness is brought on by a novel coronavirus species called SARS-CoV-2. To develop antidotes for this virus, several investigations on lead compounds derived from medicinal plants have been carried out. The plant *Hylocereus costaricensis* produces the super red dragon fruit, which is one of the fruits with a high betacyanin concentration. In addition to its immunomodulatory and anti-inflammatory properties, betacyanin also has antiviral properties. Thus, the purpose of this study was to compare betacyanin with the nelfinavir and hydroxychloroquine sulfate that have been suggested for the treatment of COVID-19 and assess its interaction with many SARS-CoV-2 receptors by measuring its binding affinity. This study was an in-silico investigation that evaluated binding affinity simulations based on molecular docking utilizing computer software. According to the study's findings, betacyanin had a high affinity for many receptors, suggesting that it might be used as a lead chemical to combat COVID-19. According to its binding affinity value, betacyanin's efficacy was on par with that of hydroxychloroquine sulfate and nelfinavir, which

the WHO recommends as COVID-19 treatment agents [30].

Millions of people are impacted by seasonal influenza globally, whereas the influenza A virus (IAV) is the cause of pandemics and yearly epidemics, which result in the most severe diseases that cause hospitalization or death for patients. There is a race against time to find antiviral medications because IAV poses a threat to the next worldwide influenza pandemic. Unique reddish-violet pigments that contain nitrogen and are soluble in water, betacyanins have been shown to have antiviral qualities against the dengue virus. This investigation aimed to examine the antiviral action of red pitahaya (*Hylocereus polyrhizus*) betacyanins on IAV-infected lung epithelial A549 cells. Four betacyanins—phyllocactin, hydrocoerenin, betanin, and isobetanin—were identified in the betacyanin fraction by HPLC and LC-MS analysis of the extracted betacyanin. At doses below 100 µg/mL, betacyanin fractions were not harmful to A549 cells, according to a cytotoxicity experiment. In IAV-infected cells, betacyanin fraction doses of 12.5, 25.0, and 50.0 µg/mL decreased the virus and inhibited the development of the viral cytopathic impact for up to 72 hours. The antiviral efficacy of red pitahaya betacyanin against IAV in vitro was demonstrated by the downregulation of protein and mRNA nucleoprotein expression levels following treatment with 25.0 and 50.0 µg/mL of betacyanin fractions after 24 hours [31]. The antiviral properties of betacyanins from red spinach (*Amaranthus dubius*) and red pitahaya (*Hylocereus polyrhizus*) against dengue virus type 2 (DENV-2) were examined in this work. Betacyanin fractions were obtained by extracting the pulp of red pitahaya and red spinach leaves using methanol, sub-fractionation, and Amberlite XAD16N column chromatography. Red pitahaya and red spinach betacyanin fractions had half-maximal cytotoxicity concentrations of 4.346 and

2.287 mg/ml on Vero cells, respectively. Red pitahaya's betacyanin fraction has a half-maximal inhibitory concentration (IC₅₀) of 125.8 µg ml⁻¹ and a selectivity index (SI) of 5.8. Red spinach's betacyanin fraction has an IC₅₀ value of 14.62 µg ml⁻¹ and a SI of 28.51. The betacyanin fraction from red pitahaya (IC₅₀ of 126.70 µg/ml; 95.0% virus inhibition) and red spinach (IC₅₀ value of 106.80 µg/ml; 65.9% virus inhibition) had a direct virucidal impact against DENV-2 when tested at the highest non-toxic betacyanin concentration. In vitro, DENV-2 was suppressed by betacyanin fractions from red pitahaya and red spinach [32].

Prebiotic Properties

Distilled water, 100, 500, and 1000 mg/kg DFO, 1000 mg/kg FOS, or 109 CFU were given to the mice in this investigation. For one week, take *Bifidobacterium animalis* every day; for two weeks, take certain treatments. Colon morphological features, smooth muscle (SM) contractions, and motility patterns were evaluated together with the analysis of gastrointestinal transits. When compared to the control group, the administration of FOS, 500, and 1000 mg/kg DFO markedly enhanced fecal production. Compared to DFO groups, mice treated with FOS and bifidobacteria showed a decrease in gut transit duration and an increase in upper gut transit. DFO enhanced the amount of colonic non-propagation contractions and fecal pellet velocity, according to spatiotemporal maps of colonic wall movements. These findings were in line with those of groups treated with FOS and bifidobacteria. Additionally, DFO lengthened the duration and amplitude of colonic SM contractions. In every group, histological stains revealed normal goblet cells, crypts, epithelia, and SM thickness. In summary, DFO functioned as a bulk-forming and stimulant laxative to enhance intestinal motility and fecal production while increasing colonic SM contractions without causing morphological changes. DFO may therefore improve

gastrointestinal motility issues and support gut health when taken as a dietary supplement [33]. With total concentrations of 86.2 and 89.6 g/kg, respectively, glucose, fructose, and a few oligosaccharides were the main carbohydrates found in white and red-flesh pitayas (dragon fruit). The extraction solvent has an impact on the extract's molecular weight distribution. At room temperature (28 ± 2 °C), 80% ethanol extraction was used to achieve the greatest oligosaccharide content (27.40%), which contained fractions with molecular weights of 273–275, 448–500, and 787–911 Da. By cultivating yeast, the low molecular weight fraction—which included fructose and glucose—was effectively eliminated. Mass spectrometry was used to validate the molecular weights of mixed oligosaccharides (716, 700, 490, and 474 Da). The mixed oligosaccharides demonstrated resistance to hydrolysis by human α-amylase and fake human gastric juice, with maximal hydrolysis rates of 34.88% and 4.04%, respectively. It was also discovered that the mixed oligosaccharides might promote the growth of bifidobacteria and lactobacilli [34].

Because of its nutritious advantages, dragon fruit is growing in popularity. Due to its oligosaccharide content, it has been suggested as a possible natural prebiotic source. The purpose of this study is to assess the prebiotic qualities of oligosaccharides found in dragon fruit meat. Due to their resistance to hydrolysis by human α-amylase in the mouth, artificial human gastric juice in the stomach, and human α-amylase with sucrase, the oligosaccharides are considered indigestible. The greatest hydrolysis rates were 6.7%, 0.6%, and 4.81%, respectively. *Bacteroides* and *Clostridium* populations decreased, whereas bifidobacteria and lactobacillus populations increased as a result of fecal fermentation of the oligosaccharides. Additionally, with a prebiotic index (PI) of 0.41, the oligosaccharide fermentation in the feces showed a beneficial

prebiotic impact. At concentrations of 860, 265, 15.95, and 29.63 mM, respectively, acetic acid, lactic acid, propionic acid, and butyric acid were generated. These short-chain fatty acid mixtures can inhibit Caco-2 cells, which may lower the risk of colon cancer [35]. DFO (dragon fruit oligosaccharides) showed prebiotic properties that can control the gut microbiota, generate SCFAs (short-chain fatty acids) in the three-stage continuous colon system, and markedly boost the proliferation of IgG and IgA at a dose of 4 g kg⁻¹ day over two weeks in the rat study. It also significantly increased the number of beneficial bacteria and decreased the number of harmful bacteria through both direct and indirect pathways. DFO is safe to use at levels up to 4 g kg⁻¹, and it can thereby modify the gut flora and boost the gut immune response [36].

Healthy eating is quite popular and has a great impact on health. According to our earlier research, dragon fruit oligosaccharides (DFOs) are safe, boost the immune system in rats, and have prebiotic properties that balance the gut microbiota in a system that mimics a human colon. In a human experiment, the effects of DFO on immunological activation, gut microbe regulation, and the relationship between gut microbiota and nutrition were examined. This clinical investigation was double-blind, randomized, and placebo-controlled. 107 healthy people were split up into three groups and given DFO in drinking water dosages of 4 and 8 g/day for four weeks in a row, while the placebo group was kept in the dark. Consuming 4 g of DFO per day raised IgA levels (11.31 mg/dL or 10.95% from baseline), whereas consuming 8 g per day significantly boosted the growth of *Faecibacterium* (1.99%) and *Bifidobacterium* spp. (8.41%) and reduced dangerous bacteria, particularly *Escherichia coli* (8.44%). Significant ($p < 0.05$) associations between particular microbial groups and intakes of particular macro- and micronutrients were found

when the link between gut microorganisms and nutrient consumption was investigated. For healthy people, the recommended daily intake of DFO was determined to be 4 g to increase IgA levels and 8 g to support favorable gut bacteria [37].

Anti-Ulcer Properties

DFE's (dragon fruit extract) effects were assessed in Sprague-Dawley rats using a model of stomach injury caused by indomethacin. All rats in the experimental model fasted for twenty-four hours. DFE was given to the ulcer-induced groups after this time. All groups, except the HEALTHY and DFE1000 groups, received an oral gavage of indomethacin at a dosage of 25 mg/kg an hour after this application. The experiment came to an end when the rats were put to death under a high-dose anesthetic six hours after the indomethacin was administered. The stomach tissues in the study were subjected to macroscopic and microscopic investigations to examine the ulcerative region, molecular and biochemical analyses to investigate oxidative damages, and molecular analyses to determine the mechanism of action of indomethacin and DFE. GSH (glutathione) antioxidant levels dropped in the indomethacin group, while oxidative stress-related indicators including MDA, BAX, and Caspase 3 sharply rose. When compared to the ulcer group, these metrics were shown to be considerably improved in the DFE 500 mg/kg and DFE 1000 mg/kg groups; in particular, the DFE 1000 mg/kg group's findings were comparable to those of the famotidine group. We saw that all of our previous findings were corroborated by our histopathology results. Because dragon fruit extract inhibited Caspase 3, BAX, and Cox-2 and activated Cox-1, it also reduced MDA levels and raised GSH levels, protecting against ulcer damage caused by indomethacin [38].

CONCLUSION

To sum up, dragon fruit is a fruit that is rich in nutrients and offers several health and

pharmacotherapeutic advantages. Antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, anti-ulcer, anti-obesity, and many other health advantages are provided by its remarkable nutritional makeup. To completely explore the potential of dragon fruit and its uses in medicine, more research and testing should be conducted. Nonetheless, the research currently available indicates that they are a great addition to a nutritious diet.

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